

The Concept of Folk: Interpreting its Representation in Knowledge Structure

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Received: 10-08-2025

Revised: 19-08-2025

Accepted: 29-08-2025

Abstract: *Inclusion and representation of multidimensional concepts pose a challenge to any Knowledge Organisation System. This study aims to explore how the concept of Folk has been reflected in the twenty-third edition of Dewey Decimal Classification System (DDC). It shows how the various aspects related to folk has been classified in the scheme, as well as highlights the interpretational difficulties that a classifier might face while representing folk in the Universe of Knowledge. Not only so there are instances of similar terms being present in DDC making the classification context dependent. It also examines how some of the documents on folk and its diverse concepts are classified in the Library of Congress (LOC) and National Library of India (NLI). The findings reveal that the concept of folk is vastly diverse and requires proper understanding and interpretation.*

Keywords: Folk, Folklore, Library Classification, Dewey Decimal Classification Scheme, Library of Congress, National Library of India.

1 Introduction

Transfer of knowledge, orally or through formal institutions, across time and generation holds significant historical, social, and cultural importance. The term ‘Folk’ reflects the idea of a collective identity and shared experiences associated with ‘a way of life’ of a specific community that is passed through oral transmission or by common practices, generation after generations. It includes traditions and customs; faiths and beliefs; diverse forms of cultural expressions like dance, drama, and music; arts, crafts, and architecture; medicine; literary manifestations like lores, legends, fables, proverbs, mythologies, poetry, drama etc. Historically ‘folk’ was often associated with rural, agrarian, non-literate communities. With time the idea of folk evolved to include even urban, educated, and advanced groups of people who share some points of commonality and cohesion.

Dundes (1980) defined folk as “any group of people whatsoever who shares at least one common factor. It does not matter what the linking factor is – it could be a common occupation, language, or religion-but what is important is that a group is formed for whatever reason it calls its own”. So, a ‘folk

identity' can get created based on several factors viz.: ethnicity, occupation, region, religion, common history, etc. Such identities pave the way for the development of unique folk cultures that encompass all their tangible and intangible representations, viz. material cultures (arts and artifacts, architecture, handicrafts etc.); oral traditions (folklores, myths, legends, riddles, etc.); customs (rituals, festivals, etc.); performing arts (dance, music, songs). The purview of 'Folk' as a concept is therefore diverse and multidimensional. It cannot be considered just as a group of people with certain commonality. Rather 'Folk' represents a knowledge system whose understanding requires perspective of several disciplines such as Anthropology, History, Literature, Performing Arts, Sociology, Medicine, Architecture, etc.

Any library classification scheme represents innumerable multifaceted domains. These domains include concepts like Environment, Rural, Urban, Women, Disability, Disaster, Water and so on. But the disciplinary structure of the classification schemes inevitably results in their scattering under distinctly separate subject fields. Although initially this scattering might not pose a challenge, however, the growth of literary warrant of any of these domains and its emergence as significant research areas, certainly leads to serious issues in easily locating all related documents on the specific concept together. Moreover, after a period, there might emerge a separate discipline, further necessitating the need to bring together all related documents of the concerned subject matter. For instance, a whole new academic discipline called 'Folklore Study' has emerged "the subject matter of which comprises the sum total of traditionally derived and orally or imitatively transmitted literature, material culture, and custom of subcultures within predominantly literate and technologically advanced societies" (Folklore, n.d.). The need to bring together documents that are related to the core idea of 'Folk' and fall under the scope of the subject field becomes inevitable. For the concept of Folk, the area of concern is not just its scattering but also the challenge of interpreting the various related aspects. Similarly, the presence of a single term under two or more subjects further leads to considerable difficulties. Understanding the context and proper interpretation therefore becomes crucial in determining its rightful position in the universe of subject.

As the concept of 'Folk' is dynamic, and highly context dependent, exploring its treatment will give an insight into the representation of 'Folk' in a Library Classification Scheme.

2 Review of Literature

Exploring treatment of disciplines or subjects in library classification schemes have been attempted by many. Dong-Geun, & Ji-Suk (2001) highlighted the bias in representation of the religion 'Christianity' spread from 220-280 and discussed the scope for expansion of the Religion 200 class in Dewey Decimal classification scheme (DDC). Fields & Connell (2004) explored the dealing of the subject Home Economics, its number relocation, terminological changes and placement biases in the various editions of DDC. Saha & Hatua (2019) dealt with Humanities and its representation as a discipline in the twenty third edition of DDC. Studies have been conducted to investigate the inclusion and reflection of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary subjects in classification schemes. Comparative study of selected fused main subjects in Colon Classification (CC), Universal Decimal Classification (UDC) and DDC were attempted by Neelameghan and Gopinath (1972); Husain (1989) evaluated the accommodation capability of Colon Classification seventh edition focusing on two subjects viz Astronomy and Astrophysics. A comparison of interdisciplinary representations in DDC, UDC and CC was made by Bhattacharya (2006) on subjects under Science and Technology. An investigation on

subject development and number relocation in classification schemes was carried out by Gopinath and Seetharama (1975) on three subjects viz: Biochemistry, Marketing and Survey Research Methodology. While these studies focused on understanding disciplinary/interdisciplinary representations, efforts have also been made to analyze multifaceted concepts that have over the year gathered considerable literary warrants. Biros (2013) carried out a study on 'environment' for which he analyzed the environmental dictionary present in British National Library and identified the different sub-categories in which these dictionaries have been classified. Balaji (2019) attempted to investigate the domain 'Urban' as reflected in three classification schemes- Library of Congress Classification Scheme, Universal Decimal Classification and Dewey Decimal Classification. The paper focused on the different vocabularies and disciplines from which the subject Urban Studies draws its subject matters from. The reflection of 'Children' in Dewey Decimal Classification was dealt with by Pal, Mondal & Bhattacharya (2019) in their study. Ghosh & Das (2019) showed a comparative study on the treatment of 'Persons with Disabilities' between DDC and UDC. The findings of the study showed that UDC provides for the in-depth subject coverage suitable for specialist library collections. Sanyal (2022) discussed the treatment of 'gender spectrum' in Dewey Decimal classification using N-Gram analysis. The literature search shows that most of the previous works concentrated on identifying the treatment or representation of the subjects or multifaceted concepts in a discipline-based classification schemes and very little work has been done in understanding the scattering of the domains and their overlapping of ideas posing a problems in understanding the correct position of classifying a document, leaving the decision to a large extent on the ability of the classifier to interpret the subject matter of the document to be classified. A study focusing on such problems becomes pertinent. This study thus attempts to identify the scattering, problems in interpreting and classifying the multifaceted concept 'Folk'.

3 Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to identify the problems in interpreting and classifying a multidimensional concept of 'Folk'. In doing so the study attempted:

- To find the main classes under which 'Folk' is represented in DDC.
- To study the interpretational challenges in representation of the various aspects of the 'Folk'.
- To identify any existing gap in the inclusion of 'Folk'
- To study how documents on Folk and related aspects are classified in libraries.

4 Methodology

At first, a thorough document search was conducted to identify the various aspects that fall within the purview of the concept of 'Folk.' Literature search included dictionaries, encyclopedias as well as syllabuses of universities that have courses on Folklore Studies as separate disciplines. In the second stage the listed aspects were searched in the 23rd edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) to identify its positions in the classification scheme. In the third stage documents (books) corresponding to the listed search terms for each of the aspects were searched and retrieved from the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) to understand how these domains are classified. For this the Library of Congress OPAC and the National Library of India OPAC have been studied. Finally, analysis and interpretations of the collected data have been done to fulfil the objective of the study.

5 Scope and Limitations

The study is restricted to the reflection of the concept of 'Folk' in the twenty-third edition of Dewey Decimal Classification only. Also, due to unavailability of Dewey Decimal class numbers in all national library OPACs only the Library of Congress OPAC and National Library of India OPAC were used to retrieve documents for exploring the class number assigned. Class number assigned to 'Books' were only taken into consideration. As the number of retrieved books from both the OPACs were large, so, due to time constraints, a purposive sampling method was adopted to select the books for the fulfillment of the objective of the paper.

6 Significance of the Study

Classifying multifaceted concepts is a challenge. Any such concept has high chances of showing conceptual overlapping resulting in indistinctness in the subject matter of a document. Comprehending the context and properly interpreting the subject matter of the document to be classified becomes necessary to put it in its right place in the Universe of Subject. Moreover, the perspectives of interpretation might vary depending upon the main subject that is being dealt with. In DDC, mapping 'folk' and exploring its various treatments under different Main classes will help library professionals in understanding the interpretational significance and relevance in classifying multifaceted concepts like 'folk' more accurately.

7 Data Analysis and Interpretation

7.1 Reflection of Folk in Twenty-Third edition of DDC

Table 1: Folk & its corresponding class numbers as reflected in DDC

Main Class in DDC	Sub Class in DDC	Topic	Class No.
Social Science 300	Culture & institutions 306	Folkways	306
	Customs, etiquette, folklore 390	Folklore	398
		History, Geographic Treatment, biography of folklore	398.09
		Folk Literature	398.2
		Real phenomenon as subjects of folklore	398.3
		Para natural and legendary phenomenon as subject of folklore	398.4
		Riddles	398.6
		Jokes and Jests	398.7
		Rhymes and Rhyming Games	398.8
	Proverbs	398.9	

Main Class in DDC	Sub Class in DDC	Topic	Class No.
Technology 600	Medicine & health 610 Pharmacology and therapeutics 615 Specific therapies and kinds of therapies 615.8	Folk Remedies	615.88
Arts and recreation 700	Graphic arts & decorative arts 740 Decorative arts 745	Folk Arts	745
	Music 780 General principles & musical forms 781 Elements of music 781.2	Folk Music Modes	781.263
	Traditions of music 781.6	Folk Music	781.62
	Recreational and performing arts 790 Indoor games and amusements 793 Social, folk, national dancing 793.3	Folk Dance	793.31

Main Class in DDC	Sub Class in DDC	Topic	Class No.
Literature (Belles-lettres) and rhetoric 800	Rhetoric and collections of literary texts from more than two Literatures 808	Folk Poetry	808.81
	Collections of literary texts from more than two Literatures 808.8	Folk Drama	808.2

The above table reveals that the concepts relating to 'Folk' is scattered under four main classes viz.: 300 Social Science, 600 Technology, 700 Arts & Recreation and 800 Literature. Under 300 Social Science, Folk is classed as 'Folkways' in 306 'Culture & institutions'. It is also classed under 390 'Customs, Etiquette, folklore'. Class number 398 is specifically assigned to the concept of 'folklore' under which almost all aspects of folklore has been dealt with. This includes History, geographic and biographical treatment of folklore; Folk literature; Any real or paranormal phenomenon that feature as a subject of folklore, legends; as well as riddles, jokes, rhymes, proverbs that are part of folklore. Under 600 'Technology' Folk is reflected under 610 Medicine class. Folk remedies have been given class number 615.88 under 615 Pharmacology and therapeutics. In 700 'Arts and recreation' 745 Decorative Arts has a note 'Class Here Folk Arts'. Under 780 'Music', 'Folk Music Modes' have class number 781.263 and 'Folk Music' have class number 781.62. Similarly, under 790 'Recreational and performing arts' Folk Dance has the class number 793.31. Under Literature 800 'Folk Poetry' and 'Folk Drama' are assigned class number 808.81 and 808.82 respectively as collection of literary text from more than two literatures.

Table 2: Folk & its corresponding class numbers as reflected in Tables of DDC

Table No.	Topic	Class Number
Subdivisions for Works by or about More than One Author (Table 3B)	Folk Poetry, Prose, Poem	-1
	Folk Drama	-2
Notation to Be Added Where Instructed in Table 3B, 700.4, 791.4, 808-809 (Table 3C)	Customs, etiquette, folklore	-3559

Other than the Main Classes, Table 3B also reflects the concept of 'Folk Poetry, Prose, Poem' having the class number -1; and 'Folk Drama' -2. On the other hand, in table 3C -3559 is assigned for 'Customs, etiquette, folklore'.

Table 3: Folk & its corresponding class numbers as reflected in Index of DDC

Main Class in DDC	Topic	Index Class Number
Technology 600	Folk Medicine	610
Arts and recreation 700	Folk Song	782.42162
Biography	Folk Singers Folk Musicians	782.421 620 092 (Index) 781.620.092 (Index)

The term 'Folk Medicine' has been assigned class number 610 (Medicine & health) in the index only. The class number for 'Folk Song' needs to be constructed following the add instruction as given under 782.4. However, the class number for folk song has an index entry having the class number 782.421 62. For folk song of any region further 'add instructions' are given. Again, few of such regional folk songs have dedicated class number in the index viz: 782.4216213 (American Folk Song); 782.421622 (English Folk Song) 782.4216241 (French Folk Song) 782.4216231 (German Folk Song) 782.42162691 (Portuguese Folk Song) 782.421629171 (Russian Folk Song) 782.4216261 (Spanish Folk Song). Biographical treatment of folk singers or folk musicians is assigned class number as per instructions. In the index there is entry of already constructed class numbers for both.

7.2 Interpretational Challenges in representation of the various aspects of 'Folk' in DDC

Identifying the interpretational challenges in classifying folk necessitates the understanding of the basic concepts that are represented and how they might lead to a conflict in determining the class numbers. As revealed from Table 1 the most explicit location of Folk concepts is in 398 Folklore. This class number or any of its subordinate class number can be assigned to documents which have folk concepts as its core subject area. Under 398 Folklore is treated in two distinct ways: first 398.2 deals folk as literature and secondly 398.3-398.4 considers the themes of any folklore as social and cultural phenomenon. Both categories cover almost similar themes and subjects, however, have completely different implications. Class Number 398.2 includes folktales, fairy tales, fables, as well as any work of their criticism / critical appraisal. It includes provisions to represent folk literature by language in class number 398.204 having instruction to add language from Table 6, example 'Folktales of Bengali speaking areas of the world' 398.2049144; folk literature of specific continents, countries & localities in class number 398.209 having instruction to add area notation from Table 2, for example 398.20954 for 'Folk Literature of India'. However, for 'French Folktales from France' it is the place that gets precedence over language. Class number 398.20944 will be assigned to it. Other than this, there are provisions of class number for folklore on different topics and themes, for example paranatural beings of human, tales about places, time, animals, plants, ghost stories etc. On the other hand, Class number 398.3-398.4 deals with history and criticism of the themes/subjects of folklore. The works in consideration here treats the themes it terms of their social and cultural significance. It includes themes on 'real phenomenon' like time, weather, scientific themes as well as 'paranatural and legendary phenomenon' like folk beliefs, legendary plants and animals etc. Thus, as mentioned in DDC the class number for 'Folkloristic Ghost Story' will be 398.25 and 'Ghost as a subject of folklore' would be 398.47. Similarly, the theme 'Place' has three different representations: Folklore of India will be

398.20954 and Folktales on India will be 398.23254 both representing folk literature whereas 'India as a subject of folklore' will be classed as 398.32954 under Real phenomena as subjects of folklore. The class 398 also includes 'Riddles', 'Jokes', 'Rhymes'-including lullabies, tongue twisters, proverbs along with Folk aphorisms.

While folklore has a detailed representation in DDC, there are areas that creates interpretational challenges in deciding class numbers. One such area is determining whether the document in consideration is folk literature or general literature. Anonymity and oral transfer are not enough to identify a folklore. There also exists anonymous classics that have more literary value even if transferred across generation orally. The manual of DDC 23rd edition explains this with the example of 'Njals Saga' which they have classified under literature having 839.63 as the class number. Similarly having an author does not qualify a book to be a classic or literature. For example, as mentioned in the manual 'Collection of folktales by Grimm brothers' will always be classed as Folk literature as they are mere collections of already existing folktales and the authors have little contribution to it. But Hans Christian Andersen's collection of Fairy Tales is not a part of folklore but rather is classed under 800 Literature with 839.8136 as the specific class numbers. Again, anonymous classics can also be classed with subjects. This is especially evident in case of Mythologies. Mythologies having high religious, theological or ritualistic values are classed under 200 Religion. For example, Jataka Tales will have the class number 294.382325. However, "myths or mythology presented in terms of cultural entertainment or, especially, as representative of the early literary expression of a society, even if they are populated by gods and goddesses" (Dewey, 2011) must be classed under 398.2 Folklore. For non-religious mythology and legends that have social themes or heroes that are not related to religious beliefs again the class number is under 389.2 Folklore. Thus, classifying mythology especially those featuring gods and goddesses needs to be interpreted true to its context before assigning a class number. Collected works on folk literature faces another challenge when the document, in hand, have writings belonging to more than two literatures. In such cases Folk Drama or Folk Poetry are classed in Literature class under 808 dealing with literary text from more than two literature. This leads to scattering of folk literature under two distinct Main classes: Folk literature and Literature in general.

This ambiguity is present not just for literature. As music, art, dance, medicine, plants, animals etc all appears as themes in folklore understanding which folk music, art or dance to be classed as folklore and which under 700 Arts and recreation is important. Not all documents dealing with folk music and dance will be classed as folk music, song or dance. Music as a theme of folklore definitely will find its place under 398 but any modern expression of folk music will be classes under 781.62 'Folk Music'. So, the question to decide whether the item to be classified represents cultural tradition or a representation of modern artistic performance lies with the classifier. The line is often blurry and might lead to scattering materials in a library. Moreover, the provision to classify folk music originating from a specific ethnic group or national group falls under 781.62 with instruction to add notation from Table 5 i.e. the table dealing with ethnic and national groups, For example Spanish folk music 781.6261. Similar types of contradiction also exist in case of Folk Song and Folk dance. Any item of cultural traditional manifestation of folk dance must be classed under 398 whereas any modern-day expression of the folk dance will be classed under 793.31 Folk Dance under recreational and performing arts. For Folk Arts if represented as decorative item will be classed as 745 Folk Arts.

There are numerous such terms related to 'Folk' that have both traditional and modern manifestations. The modern manifestations include the original folk concepts and ideas but neither form folk literature

nor are true cultural and social expressions of folkways or folk cultures. Rather they are more like an adaption of those ideas into the modern context. Thus, they do not represent the folk culture true to its sense.

7.3 Gap in the inclusion of 'Folk' in DDC

Table 4: Selected terms related to Folk not reflected in DDC

Terms	Title of the book	Class Numbers in LOC OPAC
Folk Culture	Folk Culture	306.0954
Folk Customs	Folk customs / by Ellyn Sanna	398.097
	Welsh Folk Customs	398.09429
Folk Medicine	African American folk healing.	398.208996073
	Folk medicine / by Peter Sieling	398.353
	Folk medicine in America today / John Heinerman	615.50973
Folk Law	Folk law:essays in the theory & practice of Lex non scripta	340.5
	Burmese law tales; the legal element in Burmese folklore	398.209591
Folk Architecture	Spanish folk architecture	720.946
	Kentucky folk architecture	728
	Romanian folk architecture	720.9498

While carrying out the literature search a list of folk related concepts were made representing the various dimensions of 'Folk'. While most of the terms representing the concepts have been found either directly or through add instructions, some of the terms were found to have no direct terminological representation. The above table shows selected terms that have significant connection to the concept of 'Folk' but does not have an assigned class number given in DDC. The table also reveals class numbers assigned to some retrieved books from the Library of Congress OPAC on those concepts. 'Folk Culture' represents a way of life and the book retrieved is classified under 306 'Culture & institutions' with added number of 54 India. Similarly, a book on Folk customs is simply classified under 398 Folklore. Folk Medicine has only an index entry. Here it is observed from the table that three books were retrieved out of which two books were assigned class number under Folklore and one under 615.8 'Specific therapies and kinds of therapies' in the main class 610 Medicine. Similar is the case for 'Folk Laws'. Between the two retrieved books, one is classed in Folklore and the other under 340 Law. Another term that had no terminological representation is Folk Architecture, also sometimes referred to as vernacular architecture. Out of the three books two were placed directly under 720 'Architecture' and one under 728 'Residential and related buildings' with little representation of the concept of folk. A further conceptual study will reveal that there are many other such folk related terms that do not have distinct representation in DDC and therefore can pose serious ambiguity in classifying them. But again, a thorough and logical interpretation of the context and purpose of the theme both the book can decide where to classify it.

7.4 Reflection in OPAC of Selected Libraries

This section represents few selected folklore books along with its class numbers as reflected in the OPAC of Library of Congress and National Library of India.

Table 5: Examples of books on 'folk' retrieved from LOC and NLI

Books	Class Number in OPAC	
	LOC	NLI
Folktales of Mexico. Edited and translated by Américo Paredes	398.20972	398.210972
Aesop's Fable	398.2452	398.24 398.21
The Complete Grimm's Fairytale	-	398.210943
Panchatantra translated from Sanskrit by Franklin Edgerton	398.2	398.24 891.23
Maryland folk legends and folk songs	398.09752	-
Bhaoyaiya lok samgit cayanika	-	782.42162
Folk music in America	784.4973	-
The Adventure of Hatim Tai	-	823 398.21

The above table shows the importance of context of any book dealing with concepts of folk. While some of them have clear reflection of their folk nature but there are instances of ambiguity as reflected in the class numbers in Table 5. One such example is Panchatantra where both LOC and NLI have classed it under Folklore, NLI also have entry where it has been placed in Literature class. Similarly, the example incase of folk songs the book 'Maryland folk legends and folk songs' is classed in 398 folklores but the book 'Bhaoyaiya lok samgit cayanika' is classed in as 782.42162 Folk songs under 782 'Vocal music'.

8. Findings

- The above study shows that the concept of folk is scattered under four main classes namely 300 Social Science, 600 Technology, 700 Arts and recreation and 800 Literature.
- The study reveals that there are interpretational challenges in deciding class numbers on Folk and its related concepts.
- There are concepts that have significant connections with folk but does not have terminological representation and assigned class numbers in twenty-third edition of DDC.
- The reflections in the OPAC of LOC and NLI supports the previous findings by showing the difference in class numbers assigned to documents dealing with same concepts.

9 Conclusion

Understanding 'folk' demands more than just identifying the concept of the document in hand. It requires in depth analysis to justly contextualize the dynamic nature of folk. Also, as the concept of folk is evolving in modern period, there are numerous scopes to include newly emerging concepts such as urban legends and memes, that are now treated as a part of folk culture under Folklore Study.

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